

The meaning of dimensional space

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Abstract The concept of 0 dimension, 1 dimension, 2 dimension, and 3 dimension, the more high dimension, until infinite dimension, namely the concept of gradually increasing of dimension is non-existence. Instead, there is only a concept of infinitely great that is an one quantitative continuum. The space we see is just the difference of 1 dimension finite quantities and infinitely great quantities that is open space and is implied by change of direction. The accurate description of this one quantitative continuum is that its parts are connected each other as a unity at the infinite distance (infinitely great) relative to any orientation (all orientations) of our existence. It is unity in which its random parts is this infinitely great quantities and thus we call this unity as infinite quantities of infinite dimensions.

1 Introduction

It is vague concept in which the dimension of space in common sense is described as 0 dimension, 1 dimension, 2 dimension, and 3 dimension, etc., corresponding to undividedly 0 point, the straight line, plane surface, and curved surface, etc. To define the concept of dimension more clearly, I assume that above definition of dimension is correct and the its implications must be illustrated in axiom 1 and axiom 2¹. In axiom 1 the change in dimension is the change among finite quantities, such as change from 0 to dimension, or from 1 dimension to 2 dimension. In axiom 2 0 dimension is non-existent and change from 1 dimension to 2 dimension is the alterations from finite quantities to infinite quantities. Supposing 1 dimension is 1, then 2 dimension is ∞ (infinitely great), the formula for $\infty/1 = \infty$ is established. The more high dimension is described as ∞^n ($n \geq 3$, until $n = \infty$). In view of the common feature of the two axioms is the ability to compare sizes, and the superpositions of numerical quantities in the two axioms is gradually close to a given length quantities (or numerical quantities is gradually increase), the numerical quantities of dimension in the two axioms is also gradually increase (namely 1 dimension, 2 dimension, and 3 dimension, the more high dimension, until infinite dimension) in spite of their different definitions of dimension.

2 Main Results

Preliminaries Since axiom 1 and axiom 2 are logically incorrect, the above definition of dimension does not exist. From revised axiom 1² (in this article I call revised axiom 1 as axiom 3) the exact definition and some properties of dimension are obtained.

Theorem 1 In axiom 3 the infinitesimal is defined as 1 dimension quantities of finite length ‘—’ without a size. The exact definition for this 1 dimension ‘—’ means: ① A straight line of finite length. ② Without a size. ③ One-dimension absoluteness. That is, in terms of extensibility of space, it is a straight line in 1 dimension, while in other orientations, it is 0 dimension. See figure 1.

Figure1 A straight line of finite length.without a size. In terms of extensibility of space,it is a straight line in 1 dimension,while in other orientations, it is 0 dimension.

Theorem 2 In axiom 3 the finite quantities attain to the accumulations of infinitely many quantities of itself by the way of change of direction,reaching infinitely great. This infinitely great (infinitely many quantities) indicated by change of direction exists in the form of one quantitative continuum. The infinitely great can be described as unlimited,open space, compressing anything outside it into nothing. The change of direction indicated that the finite quantities is not part of infinite quantities and all the parts of space we can see are this one quantitative continuum that represents infinitely great,and in which you can not compare sizes of each other and carried out by the any algorithms , such as the operations of addition,subtraction,multiplication, division.Since without position of finite quantities,accurate description of this one quantitative continuum is that its parts are connected each other as a unity at the infinite distance (infinitely great) relative to any orientation (all orientations)of our existence.Here any orientation (all orientations)of our existence is indicated accurately as infinity of space whose parts are connected each other as a unity at the infinite distance (open ,unlimited space) .For a clearer description,the terms'its parts' is used in this article,in fact the concept of 'its parts'is equal to one quantity.Seeing figure 2.Consequently,Axiom3 is denial of feature of gradually increasings of number and dimension quantites.In axiom 3, there is no concept of 0 dimension,1 dimension ,2 dimension,and 3 dimension,the more high dimension,until infinite dimension ,namely the concept of gradually increasings of dimension is non-existence.On the other hand,there is only a concept of infinitely great that is an one quantitative continuum and is not established by the any algorithms within it . Therefore, the concept of multidimension is non-existence,the space we see is just the defference of 1 dimension finite quantities and infinitely great quantities that is open space and is implied by change of direction. A conclusion is drawn that the quantitative values and dimensions are the same thing ,it is unity in which its random parts is this infinitely great quantities. Thus we call this unity as infinite quantities of infinite dimensions.

All parts are made of infinite quantities, connect each other in infinitely great distance

Figure 2 one quantitative continuum is that its parts are connected each other as a unity at the infinite distance (infinitely great) relative to any orientation (all orientations) of our existence. Here any orientation (all orientations) of our existence is indicated accurately as infinity of space whose parts are connected each other as a unity at an open, unlimited space.

Theorem 3 It is known from character 2 that no other dimension exists (such as infinite dimension is also non-existence) except for finite length quantities of 1 dimension regardless of whether the dimension in common sense (such as in axiom1 and axiom2) represents finite or infinite quantities. Taking an example, it is meaningless to talk about 1 dimension straight line that extends to infinite distance, because of even though considering it being infinite in the orientation of extending to infinite distance, it is finite in the other orientations in which axiom3 is violated. Further, it is non-existence that any extensibility of space are made of combinations of finite quantities and infinite quantities since the parts of infinitely great must be connected to form a whole at an infinite distance to conform the definition of infinitely many quantities (all parts must be infinitely quantities) in axiom 3. Seeing figure 3. We can say that the space we see is just an components of infinitely great. For the same reason, any line, or plane, or any outline of having properties of gradually increase dimension draw in space, such as circle, is meaningless. Seeing figure 4. In addition, it does not make sense for us to do differential geometry on space. The space is an infinitely great unified continuum representing all orientations (the unified whole).

Figure 3 It is meaningless to talk about 1 dimension straight line that extends to infinite distance(1) , Further,It is non-existence that any extensibility of space are made of combinations of finite quantities and infinite quantities (2).

Figure 4 The any line ,or plane,or any outline of having properties of gradually increase dimension draw in space is meaningless. additional,it does not make sense for us to do differential geometry on space .

Theorem 4 It is known from character 2 that the one quantitative continuum indicating indefinitely great connected each other (actually only one quantity) as a unity at the infinite distance relative to any orientation (all orientations) of our existence. Any parts of this one quantity's unity is itself and any operations or algorithms building on this unity is itself. Considering the concept of time, it can be known from character 2 that if we take us as the origin dot and extend it to infinite distance, its end and beginning will become a quantity at infinite distance.

So far, the exact value of any length of space and meaning of dimension of space have been described mathematically. So some readers ask what is the relationship between space and time? Taking example, How are some physical quantities such as velocity, acceleration, mass defined in axiom 3? We will describe properties of these quantities in detail in the later papers.

Reference

- 1 Qing Li .A non-continuum of the infinitesimal superposition. (preprint viXra:2008.0067)
- 2 Qing Li, The meaning of the infinitely great (preprint authorea: DOI: [10.22541/au.160822935.50569408/v1](https://doi.org/10.22541/au.160822935.50569408/v1))

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